

Advancing physics education through the PhET simulations

Otabek Umarov Abdullaevich¹, Chinniev Odilbek Khamzakulovich²

¹ PhD, teacher, Kimyo International University in Tashkent Samarkand branch,
otabekumarov@kiut.uz

² Teacher, Kimyo International University in Tashkent Samarkand branch,
odilhamzaqulovich@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17624509>

Abstract

Digitalization has had a profound impact on education, enabling educators to teach exact and natural sciences such as physics, chemistry, biology, and mathematics with greater ease. By using virtual simulations and online platforms, lecturers can overcome traditional teaching limitations and create more interesting and effective learning environments. This paper outlines the importance of digitalization, with a focus on physics as a model discipline, and discusses virtual laboratories, so-called PhET Interactive Simulations.

Key words: Digitalization, virtual simulations and laboratories, buoyancy.

Introduction

The rapid development of digital technologies has been helping nearly every sector of modern life, including education. Traditional teaching methods in exact and natural sciences have typically involved lectures, textbooks, and laboratories. These methods often convey abstract theories or give access to experimental environments. Digitalization can offer new opportunities to improve teaching and learning through virtual laboratories, simulations, and online platforms [1-3]. The physics subject deals with phenomena ranging from the smallest particles to the largest structures. Since many of these concepts are abstract or mathematically complex, they are often studied in a university laboratory. Digitalization tools can help address these difficulties in several ways. In the virtual laboratories, for example, students can experiment with mechanics, molecular physics, electromagnetism, optics, and even thermodynamics in order to reproduce real experimental phenomena under various conditions by setting. Such a visual lab is the PhET Interactive Simulations (<https://phet.colorado.edu/>) [2-3], which is a research-based platform developed at the University of Colorado Boulder. This platform can support both editors and students in teaching and learning science and mathematics. It can offer a large collection of experimental actions and downloadable simulations in physics, chemistry, and mathematics. Each simulation might provide an interesting interface where students can manipulate variables such as force, velocity, time, mass, or electric charge and immediately measure and observe the results obtained. For teachers, they can integrate simulations into their lectures and use them as virtual laboratories to make students attend lectures. Even though virtual laboratories do not completely cover physical experimentation, PhET simulations might provide an understandable and effective supplement, especially where students have difficulties understanding complex phenomena.

Results and discussion

Let's take buoyancy, for example, to explore gravity, buoyant force, and the processes of floating and drowning. In Fig. 1, there are two objects (1A and 1B) having different density, but the same masses (where the gravity force is 39.2 Newton (due to the $P=mg=4*9.8$ N)). By observing this simulation, students can easily imagine why object 1A is drowning and object 1B is floating in the water.

Fig. 1. Buoyancy simulations using two objects with various densities.

Let's find out the Archimedes (buoyant) force using the experimental PhET simulations (as in Fig. 1). Gravity force of the mass is 39.2 Newton in the air, while this gravity force in the water is equal to 10.4 N (see Fig. 2). Student can easily find out what the buoyant force, which is difference between the gravity forces in the air and water, towards upward from downward that is $F_A = P_{\text{air}} - P_{\text{water}} = 28.8$ N. In addition to these, students can have visual imaginations about fluid displaced, directions of the forces of gravity and buoyant, or fluid density.

Fig. 2. Demonstration of finding out the buoyant force using the virtual PhET simulations.

Additionally, students can have a try different sections (like “Explore”, “Lab”, “Shapes”, and “Applications”) of this experiment related to the buoyancy as described in Fig. 3.

Summary

Virtual Labs have become an indispensable element in the teaching of physics and science, enabling visualization of abstract and complex concepts. Such Labs can bring students closer to real scientific research and make students interested in their subjects [4]. Achievements such as interactive simulations PhET have made science education more interesting, special, and globally (most of them freely) accessible. Looking ahead, digitalization tools will continue to play an important role in attracting students to the challenges of technological innovation. Another significant aspect of such Labs is that they can be very beneficial for those organisations, such as

a university that has been established recently, because in the beginning, those universities may face financial difficulties with buying expensive experimental tools.

References

1. Semenikhina, Olena Volodymyrivna, et al. "The use of virtual physics laboratories in professional training: the analysis of the academic achievements dynamics", (2020).
2. Price, Colin B., and Ruth Price-Mohr. "PhysLab: a 3D virtual physics laboratory of simulated experiments for advanced physics learning." *Physics Education* 54.3 (2019): 035006.
3. Wieman, C., Adams, W., & Perkins, K. (2008). PhET: Simulations that enhance learning. *Science*, 322(5902), 682–683.
4. Lahme, S. Z., Klein, P., Lehtinen, A., Müller, A., Pirinen, P., Rončević, L., & Sušac, A. (2023). Physics lab courses under digital transformation, arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.08515.
5. Gilbert, J. K. (2005). *Visualization in Science Education*. Springer Science & Business Medi